

Redesign of the Snakemake Workflow Catalog

Snakemake Hackathon 2025 - Report

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Description

This work was completed as part of the Snakemake Hackathon 2025.

The [Snakemake Workflow Catalog](#) is the main collection and entry point for scientists and other users to deposit, access and try out Snakemake workflows. The catalog is a statically but regularly built website hosted on Github. It collects new workflows by searching Github for appropriate workflow repos, tests them automatically and adds them to the website. However, the design of the catalog was different from the other websites of the Snakemake ecosystem, and harder to maintain.

In this series of changes, the entire front end of the catalog has been re-designed to be in line with the other Snakemake (catalog) pages. It is now built using python with [sphinx](#), the [sphinxawesome theme](#), and markdown templates that are populated using the [jinja](#) package. Notable changes and improvements are:

- deployment of the catalog: it has now a separate deploy github action workflow that builds all pages
- the 'dynamic' markdown pages are now constructed from `.md` templates in the `source/` dir
- the catalog has not just a different design but also a different, modular page layout
- there are now separate pages for general docs/instructions, 'all workflow' tables, 'top workflows' using cards, and individual workflow pages with rich documentation.

Users have the possibility to get their workflow listed in the 'standardized workflows' section with a dedicated page. For this to work, repositories additionally have to:

- have their main workflow definition named `workflow/Snakefile` (unlike for plain inclusion (see above), which also allows just `Snakefile` in the root of the repository),
- provide configuration instructions under `config/README.md`
- contain a YAML file `.snakemake-workflow-catalog.yml` in their root directory, which configures the usage instructions displayed by the workflow catalog.

Screenshot of the re-designed Catalog's landing page

Associated Project Workitem

- Redesign of the Catalog: [Pull Request 33](#), [Pull Request 36](#), [Pull Request 39](#)
- Update of the Snakemake Workflow Template: [Issue 32](#), [Pull Request 13](#)

References

The catalog can be cited as a resource:

Koester, J., & Jahn, M. (2025). Snakemake Workflow Catalog (Version 1.0.0) [Computer software]. <https://github.com/snakemake/snakemake-workflow-catalog>.

Acknowledgement

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